
The Correlation Of Population Growth And Health Centers In Satara District

Dr. Santosh Prakash Patil,

Associate Professor, Dept. of Geography, B.D.College, Patan.

Corresponding Author – Dr. Santosh Prakash Patil

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Introduction:

India is fragment country, but we see integrity in various things. It is country of large populations. India is second ranks of population in the world. It is most important and duty to provide food, clothing, and shelter to the entire population. Like these needs the health is also important. To take care of population there is intendant. Public health care system in India which is followed in Maharashtra also as one of important state. Satara district also has its own public care system. There is one district hospital. Two sub district hospitals available in Satara district. Each Tahsil has one rural hospital. Khatav Tahsil has more than 2 rural hospitals. Uneven distribution of primary health centers is recorded in study region. In this research researcher had studied the population and available health facilities in the district, like the number of doctors, nurses, ward boy and another health-related facility. In Satara district 1 Civil Hospital, 2 Sub district Hospitals, 15 Rural Hospitals 72 Primary Health centers, 400 health sub centers established. The number of health centers increased according to growth of population. In 2001, the available health facilities in Satara were less, but in 2011 the situation was changed Satara District has average availability of government medical facilities. In the early the criterion of one primary health center for 3000 population and one sub center for 5000 populations was established in Satara district

Study Region:

Satara district is one of the leading districts of Western Maharashtra. It is situated in the western part of the State and lies between north latitudes 17° 05' and 18° 11' and east longitude 73 ° 33' and 74° 54'. The total area of the district is 10480 sq. km. The district is bounded in the north by Pune district on the east by Solapur district, on the south by Sangli district and on the west by Ratnagiri district of Konkan region. Sahayadri hills of western ghat forms the western boundary, while Nira River forms the northern boundary of the district.

The district having tropical wet and dry climate. Average highest temperature 30.8 °C and average lowest temperature is 18.64°C. The average precipitation of the region is 1125.01 inch. Average elevation of the region is 742 metre. For administrative convenience, the district is divided into 11 tahsils. It has total Population 3003741 as per 2011. the male population is 1510842 and female population is 1492899 with literacy rate 82.87%. Population density is 287 persons/sq. km. The district has 15 towns. Administratively there are 11 talukas viz. Satara, Patan, Karad, Wai, Khandala, Mahableshwar, Javoli, Man, Khatav, Phaltan, Koregaon, 1739 villages, 11 Panchayat Samitis, 1488 Gram Panchayats and 8 Nagar Parishads. Sex ratio is 988.

Objectives:

In view of the above, main objectives of proposed study are as following:

1. To study the Population Growth affected Health center in study area.
2. To study the required PHCs and Doctors according to the Population Projection

Database:

The present study will be depending on primary as well as secondary data. Primary data will be collected through the questionnaire. For the purpose villagers will be chosen by stratified random sampling, and photographs, video shooting will be collected for the better understanding of the study region. Secondary data will be collected through the related reference books, magazines, published, unpublished thesis, journals, and published Govt. Report, District Census, hand book, the record of health centers, government hospitals, Newspapers, Other media reports, and related websites. And world Health Organization data

Methodology:

The present study is based on the collection of data from health care centers, hospitals and extensive field survey by the statistically tabulated, interviews, questionnaire method. Some mathematical processing will be carried out and the inferences may arrive. There is no definite method to apply to such study but statistical method, cartographic techniques.

Concentration ratio, impact method will be used wherever necessary different terms and observations used in the texts have been defined and explained in glossary at the end.

Growth of populations and Growth of Health Centers:**Population Growth:**

Population growth means positive change has taken place in the population and its impacts on frequently occurring diseases and healthcare facilities in Satara district.

To calculate the growth rate of a population, the following formula is applied by the researcher.

$$R = \frac{P_n - P_o}{P_o} \times 100$$

Population projection deals with computations of future population size and characteristics based on assumptions based about future trends infertility, mortality and migration. The formula to count the population projection is of following,

$$P_n = P_o + \frac{n(p_o - p_m)}{M}$$

P_n = population in future after a period of time

P_o = Present population

P_m = Population in the past before m years

n = Number of years for the projection

m = Number of years in the past taken in to consideration

Population Projection in the Satara district (2021)

Sr.No	Tahsil	2001	2011	Decadal growth percentage	2021	2031
1	Satara	451870	502049	11.10	552228	602407
2	Wai	189336	200269	5.77	211202	222135
3	Khandala	119819	137418	14.69	155017	172616
4	Koregaon	253138	257550	1.73	261962	266374
5	Phaltan	313627	342667	9.26	371707	400747
6	Man	199598	225634	13.04	251670	277706
7	Khatav	260951	275274	5.49	289597	291620
8	Karad	543424	584085	7.48	624746	624546
9	Patan	298095	299509	0.47	300923	302355
10	Javali	124600	106506	-14.52	88412	70318
11	M.Shwar	54546	72830	3.52	91114	109398
12	District Total	2808994	3000374	6.93	3191754	3383127

Source: Census of population during 2001 to 2011

The population in 2001 was 2808994, and it increased in the year of 2011 to 3000374. The decade's growth is 6.93%. Satara Tahsil growth was 11.10% in the decade from 2001 to 2011. Man Tahsil has the highest growth rate, at 13.45 percent. The negative growth was shown at -14.09 in the Javali Tahsil. The population projection for Satara district is 319,754 in the year 2021. The highest population will be 624746 in Karad Tahsil and the lowest will be 91114 in Mahabaleshwar Tahsil. During the period from 1991 to 2011, the

total growth of the population and the growth of health centers were not the same. But that is insufficient and there is a need for more health centers in the study region. The population projection of the study region will be 3191754 in the year 2021 and the population projection of Satara district will be 3383127 in the year 2021. The highest population will be 624746 in Karad Tahsil in 2021 and 624546 in 2031, and the lowest will be 88412 in Javali Tahsil in 2021 and 70318 in 2031.

Population Projection in the Satara district (2021):

Required PHCs and Doctors according to the Population Projection:

The growth of population in Satara district and health centers is rationally

noticed while there is need of more PHCs and doctors according to the growing population.

Required Primary Health Centers and Doctors according to the Population projection in the year 2021 and 2031:

Sr.No	Tahsil	Required Health center and doctors 2011		Required Health center and doctors 2021		Required Health center and doctors 2031	
		PHC	Doctors	PHC	Doctors	PHC	Doctors
1	Satara	9	18	18	36	20	40
2	Wai	4	16	7	14	8	16
3	Khandala	3	6	5	10	6	12
4	Koregaon	6	12	8	16	8	16
5	Phaltan	6	12	12	24	13	26
6	Man	5	10	8	16	9	18
7	Khatav	7	14	9	18	10	20
8	Karad	11	22	20	40	21	42
9	Patan	13	26	10	20	11	22
10	Javali	5	10	3	6	3	6
11	M.shwar	3	6	3	6	4	8
District total		72	144	103	206	112	224

Source: Computed by researcher

Required Primary Health Centers and Doctors according to the Population projection in the year 2021 and 2031

In Satara district, the growth of population and health centers is rationally noticed while there is a need for more PHCs and doctors according to the growing population. Table No. 6.11 shows that in the year 2021 there will be 103 PHCs and 206 doctors required to increase according to the population projection. The Satara Tahsil requires 9 PHCs and 18 doctors in the year

2021. Mahabaleshwar Tahsil requires 3 PHCs and 3 doctors. According to the population projection, in the year 2031, there will be 112 PHCs and 224 doctors. The requirement is for PHC only 1 and 2 PHCs and doctors' requirements are highest in Satara tashil at 40 and 2 doctors are required in Mahebaleshwar tashils. In respect of doctors, they may be increased by 2 in each

PHC of the above mentioned tashils. In the present chapter, the growth of health centers took place according to the growth of populations. Health centers are not noticeable, which will change in the year 2020. Health care changes have been observed from time to time, which have decreased according to the needs of the people. However, some health facilities have come into force in the district. The variation is recorded in the growth of health centers. According to the population projection, the

need for an adequate proportion of PHCs has been observed for future planning.

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